

AN INVESTIGATION ON THE CREEP BEHAVIOR OF Zn-22%Al-7%SiC(p) COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT: Experiments were conducted on Zn-22%Al/7%SiC composite prepared by variable co-deposition of multi-phase materials (VCM) to determine the effect of the reinforcement particulates on the creep deformation behavior in region I (low-stress region) and region II (intermediate-stress or superplastic region) of the sigmoidal plot between stress and strain rate, which was previously reported for the reinforcement-free counterpart alloy. The microstructures of the starting material and deformed materials were characterized using Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) and Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM). The experimental data were analyzed and discussed with emphasis on the effect of threshold stress, τ_0 , and the role of the stress dependent matrix substructures. The creep data, which extend over seven orders of magnitude of strain rate, showed that the apparent activation energy of creep, Q_a , which was stress dependent, was higher than that for commercial and high purity Zn-22%Al alloy in region I, while in region II the present materials, as the commercial and high purity alloys do, show a Q_a value in good agreement with that anticipated for grain boundary diffusion in the alloy. The microstructural data inferred from an examination of the crept specimens suggested that the origin of τ_0 may be related to the interaction between moving dislocations and dispersion particles; such dispersion particles most likely represent oxide and nitride particles that are introduced in the material as a result of processing the alloy by thermal spray and deposition.

KEYWORDS: Zn-22%Al/SiC(p) composite, creep, threshold stress, dispersion, dislocation

INTRODUCTION

The elevated temperature mechanical behavior of discontinuous silicon carbide reinforced aluminum alloys has been the subject of creep investigations [1-5] which have been motivated, in part, by a growing interest in assessing the potential of these composites for use as materials for high temperature applications. The results of these investigations show that the discontinuous silicon carbide reinforced aluminum alloys, like dispersion strengthened alloys (DS) [6], exhibit a high stress exponent, $n = \partial \ln \dot{\gamma}_s / \partial \ln \tau$, where $\dot{\gamma}_s$ is the steady-state shear strain rate and τ is the applied shear stress, and a high apparent activation energy, $Q_a > Q_D$, where Q_D is the activation energy for self-diffusion in aluminum. In addition, it was suggested [4-5, 7] that the creep behavior of silicon carbide reinforced aluminum alloys may be explained in terms of a threshold stress for creep, τ_0 , by a modified power law creep of the form:

$$\dot{\gamma}_s = A \left(\frac{\tau - \tau_0}{G} \right)^n \exp \left(- \frac{Q_c}{RT} \right) \quad (1)$$

where T is the absolute temperature, A is a unitless constant, G is the shear modulus, R is the gas constant and Q_c is the energy term.

Despite the important contributions of the above investigations, additional work is still needed (a) to investigate whether the concept of a threshold stress for creep is capable of accounting for the high apparent stress exponent for creep and the high activation energy in various discontinuous SiC-Al

composites containing different matrices and different reinforcement configurations and shapes, and (b) to study dislocation activities in the composites and to identify the nature and type of dislocation/particle interaction that may contribute to the measured threshold stress. Accordingly, an investigation has been undertaken to examine the creep behavior of Zn-22%Al/7%SiC with a two-fold purpose: (a) to determine whether the incorporation of SiC particulates into Zn-22%Al results in a higher threshold stress through a close comparison between the creep behavior of the composite and that of its unreinforced matrix alloy (reported in reference [8]) under identical experimental conditions, (b) to identify the origin of the threshold stress through careful microstructure observations on the dislocation substructures during the creep of the composite.

EXPERIMENT

The material in this research was prepared by variable co-deposition of multi-phase materials (VCM) of Zn-22%Al eutectoid alloy and SiC particulates followed by hot extrusion and heat-treatment. The resultant material has an average grain size of $2.5 \pm 0.2 \mu\text{m}$ and contains 7% volume fraction of SiC particles with average particle size of $3.5 \mu\text{m}$. Double shear specimens of shape and dimensions described elsewhere [9-10] were deformed in a silicon oil bath heated at 433, 463 and $493 \pm 1\text{K}$ and on creep machine operated under a constant load which is carefully chosen to make sure the tests run at steady state strain rates in the order of 10^{-2} and 10^{-8} s^{-1} . The specimens were air-quenched rapidly under load after a steady-state behavior was established. The strain during creep was measured with a linear variable differential transformer and amplifier, and monitored directly on a strip-chart recorder. The activation energy Q_a for creep was determined from the creep rate-stress data for different temperatures.

The grain size and morphology were examined in a Philip XL 30 Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM). To obtain a clear topological image from Zn-22%Al samples, the acceleration voltages were set between 10-12 KeV while the working distance was adjusted to about 10 mm. Samples for TEM were prepared by cutting thin slices, about 1 mm thickness, from the gage section of the deformed specimens. These slices were reduced to a thickness of about $30 \mu\text{m}$ by mechanical polishing. Thin foils were then placed in a jet-polishing machine to further reduce thickness to a few angstroms. To obtain a good thinning, the voltages and current were set to about 20V and 15 mA, respectively. The polishing solution of 20% perchloric acid and 80% ethanol was surrounded by a dry ice bath to keep the electrolyte temperature at 243K. After jet-polished, the sample was immediately rinsed in ethanol and DI water. The thin foils prepared by this technique were examined in a PHILIPS CM-20 TEM equipped with a double-tilted stage at an accelerating voltage of 200KeV. Dislocations analysis was conducted under a number of two-beam diffraction conditions.

RESULTS

The dependence of the steady-state creep rate, $\dot{\gamma}$, on the applied stress, τ , was investigated by conducting a series of double-shear tests and by plotting $\dot{\gamma}$ as a function of τ on a double logarithmic scale. Figure 1 describes this form of plot for three different temperatures of 433 K, 463 K, and 493 K. The results indicate the presence of a sigmoidal relationship between strain rate, $\dot{\gamma}$, and applied stress, τ . This sigmoidal relationship, which is similar in appearance to the trend reported for several superplastic alloys [11-13], is manifested by the presence of three regions of behavior: region I at low stresses, region II at intermediate stresses, and region III at high stresses. The stress exponents for creep in region I and region II, when the datum points are fitted by straight line, are 7.5, and 2.5, respectively. The results in region III are not sufficient to estimate the value of the stress exponent, but it is clear, on the basis of the data at 493 K, this value is larger than 4.

Fig. 1. Shear strain rate vs shear stress (logarithmic scale) for Zn-22%Al/ 7vol.%SiC having a grain size of $2.5 \mu m$ at various temperatures

Fig. 2. (a) Determination of apparent activation energies for creep at $\tau = 1.8$ MPa, $\tau = 3.7$ MPa, $\tau = 6.5$ MPa, and (b) apparent activation energy for creep, Q_a , as a function of applied stress in Zn-22%Al/ 7vol.%SiC.

Fig. 3. SEM micrographs of initial Zn-22%Al/ 7vol.%SiC showing (a) SiC distribution and (b) grain structure

Fig. 4. TEM micrographs of Zn-22%Al/ 7vol.%SiC crept at $T = 463$ K and $\tau = 3.7$ MPa showing dislocation activities at (a) a SiC particulate and (b) small dispersion particulates

The data of steady-state creep rate *vs* stress in Figure 1 were used to plot $\log \dot{\gamma}$ against $1/T$ at different stress levels. The apparent activation energies for creep, Q_a , were then determined from the slopes of the resultant straight lines. Figure 2a shows an example of $\log \dot{\gamma}$ *vs* $1/T$ at three stress levels. For $\tau = 1.8$ MPa (low-stress region), $\tau = 3.7$ MPa (transition region between low-stress region and intermediate-stress region) and $\tau = 6.5$ MPa (intermediate-stress region), the apparent activation energies, Q_a , were estimated to be 135 kJ/mol, 96 kJ/mol and 87 kJ/mol, respectively. This result indicates that Q_a increases with decreasing applied stress. Such a trend is illustrated in Figure 2b from which three additional observations may be made. First, the data define two regions: a low stress region where Q_a decreases rapidly with increasing applied stress and a high stress region where Q_a decrease slowly and finally approach a constant with increasing applied stress. Second, Q_a in low-stress region is much higher than the energy for grain boundary diffusion ($Q_{gb} = 76$ kJ/mol in Zn-22%Al alloy) [10, 14] while Q_a in intermediate-stress region is close to Q_{gb} . Third, Q_a in region I is much higher than the corresponding apparent activation energy for Zn-22%Al alloy ($Q_a = 113$ kJ/mol at $\tau = 0.55$ MPa) [8, 15-16] while Q_a in region II is close to that for the alloy material ($Q_a = 85$ kJ/mol at $\tau = 4.14$ MPa).

Figure 3 shows the typical SEM micrographs of the initial Zn-22%Al/7%SiC composite. In general, it is noted that the distribution of SiC particulates within the Zn-22%Al matrix is fairly homogeneous, and that the matrix showed an equiaxed two-phased eutectoid microstructure (see Fig. 3b). TEM observations revealed that the initial microstructure is dislocation free. The absence of dislocation substructures is due to the fact that the heat treatment used in the present investigation was very effective in removing effects associated with straining produced during extrusion of the material. Clear evidence of dislocation activities was observed in the crept material. In Figure 4a, a high dislocation density in the matrix region surrounding a big particulate is noted, while in Figure 4b, extensive interactions between dislocations and particulates (both big particulates and small dispersion particulates) can be seen in the specimens deformed in regions II. Similar dislocation/dispersion interactions were also observed in the sample deformed in region I.

DISCUSSION

The creep behavior of Zn-22%Al Alloy

As indicated by the data shown in Figure 1, the intermediate stress region for the present Zn-22%Al/7%SiC composite is characterized by: (a) a stress exponent of 2.5; (b) an activation energy that agrees with that anticipated for grain boundary diffusion. These characteristics are consistent with the previously reported creep data for reinforcement-free Zn-22%Al alloys [8], indicating that the presence of reinforcement particulates does not affect the fundamental deformation process in this region. The present result of $n = 2.5$ also supports that the dominant deformation mechanism is slip accommodated grain boundary sliding. The lack of sensitivity of the creep behavior of the Zn-22%Al alloy in the intermediate stress region to impurity content was previously reported [8]. However, the presence of the reinforcement particulates does have effects on the creep behavior in intermediate stress region: the region of $n = 2.5$ becomes narrower (covering 1.5 order of magnitude for strain rate) compared with that for reinforcement-free material (covering 3 orders of magnitude for strain rate) [8]. This narrowed intermediate-stress region can be accounted for by: (1) the stress relaxation at the reinforcement/matrix interface by diffusion flow is related to the deformation conditions including strain rate and temperature; at low temperatures and high strain rates, the stress concentration arising at dispersion particles can not be relieved and thus produces premature break down of superplastic flow, and thus shift region III towards lower strain rates; (2) the higher threshold stress associated with the particle/dislocation interactions, which will be discussed in the following paragraph, is expected to become significant and affect the creep behavior at higher stress level, and thus region I extends towards intermediate-stress region.

The origin of the sigmoidal relationship between strain rate and stress for dispersion-free superplastic alloys at low stresses was previously explained by the impurity drag on boundary dislocations [8, 15]. A threshold stress, which was suggested to be responsible for the origin of region I, must be exceeded before boundary dislocations can break away from the impurity atmosphere and produce sliding. The region I creep behavior of the Zn-22%Al/7%SiC composite is different from its reinforcement-free counterpart: (a) the stress dependence of creep rate as inferred from the value of the stress exponent, n , is higher ($n = 7.6$ for the composite and $n = 3.9$ for the alloy); (b) the temperature dependence of creep rate as measured by the value of the activation energy, Q , is higher ($Q = 135$ kJ/mol for the composite and $Q = 113$ kJ/mol for the alloy); and (c) a observable extension of region I towards higher stress level. Consideration of such data indicates that the region I creep characteristics of the present Zn-22%Al/7vol.%SiC composite are different from those documented for aluminum based solid-solution alloys but are similar to those reported for dispersion-strengthened (DS) alloys [17-18]. The creep behavior of Zn-22%Al/7vol.%SiC, unlike that of Al-based solid-solution alloys, cannot not be described over a wide range of strain rate by a simple creep power law as described by the following equation [4, 18-19]:

$$\dot{\gamma} = B \left(\frac{\tau}{G} \right)^n \exp \left(\frac{-Q_c}{RT} \right) \quad (2)$$

On the other hand, the region I creep behavior resembles that of DS alloys with regard to the high values of n and Q . This similarity suggests that the anomalous stress dependence of creep rate in the present Zn-22%Al/7vol.%SiC composite, like that in DS alloys, can be interpreted in terms of a threshold stress, τ_0 . The observed deformation is driven by an effective stress, τ_e , equal to $\tau - \tau_0$, and not by the applied stress [20-21]. In this case, the creep behavior is described by a rate equation of the form, that is, power-law creep equation becoming the modified power-law relation as shown in Equation 1. Accordingly, it is reasonable to conclude that, in addition to the segregation drag effect that takes place in reinforcement-free alloy, the increased n and Q values in the composite may be related to the presence of the reinforcement particulates that can give rise to a threshold stress for creep by serving as effective barriers to dislocation movement.

Examination of the presence of a threshold stress

A procedure similar to that applied elsewhere [2, 4, 22] is adopted to estimate the values of the threshold stresses associated with the creep of Zn-22%Al/7vol.%SiC composite. The data at a single temperature were plotted as $\dot{\gamma}^{1/n}$ against τ on a double linear scale. Under the condition that the creep data of the material obey Equation 2 and τ_0 is constant for each test temperature, the datum points will fit a straight line, whose extrapolation to zero strain rate yields the value of τ_0 at each temperature. Figure 5 shows this type of plots for $n = 2.5$ at three temperatures: 433K, 463K and 493K. The resultant values of τ_0 are listed in Table 1. The τ_0 values for Zn-22%Al alloy [8] were also shown in the table for comparison. An examination of Table 1 shows that: (a) for specific temperature, τ_0 for the composite is higher than that for the alloy; (b) the values of τ_0 are very sensitive to temperature; τ_0 decreases with increasing temperature. The dependence of τ_0 on temperature is much stronger than that attributable to the shear modulus of the alloy [10] and can be described by equation:

$$\left(\frac{\tau_0}{G} \right) = B_0 \exp \left(\frac{Q_0}{RT} \right) \quad (3)$$

Figure 5b, where the logarithm of τ_0/G is plotted against $1/T$, illustrates the validity of Equation 3. The value of Q_0 , which is determined by taking the slope of the straight line in the figure, appears to be the same for the composite and the alloy ($\approx 2.1 \times 10^4$ J/mol) [8].

Fig. 5. Determination of (a) the threshold stress, τ_0 , and (b) the energy term, Q_0 , for Zn-22%Al/ 7vol.%SiC.

Table 1. Values of τ_0 for different Zn-22%Al based materials

T, K	τ_0 (MPa)		
	High purity Zn-22%Al [8]	Commercial purity Zn-22%Al [8]	Zn-22%Al/7vol%SiC
433	~ 0	0.41	1.73
463	~ 0	0.32	1.21
493	~ 0	0.24	0.81

Table 2. Comparison between τ_0 and those estimated from various threshold models (MPa)

T, K	τ_0	Orowan stress [23-24]	Local climb [25-26]	Detachment stress [20-21]
		$\tau_o = 0.84Gb/(\lambda - d_p)$	$\tau_b = 0.3Gb/\lambda$	$\tau_d = (Gb/\lambda)(1 - K^2)^{1/2}$
433	1.73	1.65	0.59	1.67
463	1.21	1.61	0.57	1.63
493	0.81	1.58	0.56	1.59

Relaxation parameter $K = 0.85$ [4], Burgers vector $\mathbf{b} = 0.27$ nm

Fig. 6. TEM micrographs showing the interactions between dislocations and dispersion particles in Zn-22%Al/ 7vol.%SiC (a) $T = 463$ K, $\tau = 1.8$ MPa, and (b) $T = 463$ K, $\tau = 6.5$ MPa

The origin of τ_0

The difference in the magnitude of threshold stress for the Zn-22%Al alloy and the Zn-22%Al/7vol.%SiC composite can not be attributed to different levels of impurity segregation since τ_0 appears to approach a limiting value (about 0.32 MPa at 463 K) with increasing impurity level [8]. It is reasonable to examine the possibility of whether SiC particulates in Zn-22%Al/7vol.%SiC composite, like dispersion particles in DS alloys, can account for the increased threshold stress. To do this, an approach, which was employed in previous works on PM Al alloy [4, 17-19], is to substitute the geometric characteristics for SiC particulates (the average particulate size, $d_p = 3.5\mu\text{m}$, and the average interparticle spacing $\lambda = 14\mu\text{m}$) into the equations of several theoretical deformation models developed for DS alloys, namely Orowan stress model [23-24], local climb model [25-26] and detachment stress model [20-21]. However, these models are not valid for the present Zn-22%Al/7vol.%SiC composite because the matrix grain size ($d = 2.5\mu\text{m}$) is smaller than the average interparticle spacing. In addition, the finding reported by Park *et al.* [27], and general statement made by other investigators [2, 28], suggested that the threshold stresses estimated from these models are too small to account for the experimental trends noted for some coarse matrix systems, i.e., SiC particulates are not directly responsible for the threshold stresses measured in the composites.

An alternative approach for the source of the threshold stress in Zn-22%Al/7vol.%SiC composite is based on the suggestion that the oxide particles present in the Zn-22%Al matrix, as a result of manufacturing the composite by thermal spray and co-deposition, serve as effective barriers to dislocation motion and give rise to a threshold stress for creep. The validity of this suggestion is supported by two pieces of evidence: (1) TEM observations revealed extensive interactions between dislocation and dispersion particles (4~40 nm in size) in the crept materials (Fig. 6). The dislocation/dispersion particles interaction configurations shown in these figures resemble those reported for PM 6061 Al [18], PM 2124 Al [19], and DS alloys [29-30] whose creep behavior was explained in terms of a threshold stress arising from such an interaction; (2) under assumptions similar to reference [4], but with only half surface area of the droplets being available for the formation of Al_2O_3 film during atomization (the other half is Zn phase), the average planar spacing λ between the dispersion particles were estimated to be 500 nm. When this λ value (less than matrix grain size d) is substituted into the threshold stress equations shown in Table 2, the results indicated that the estimated values of the detachment stress, τ_d , and the Orowan stress, τ_o , are in good agreement with the value of τ_0 inferred from the data.

Temperature dependence of τ_0

The origin of strong temperature dependence of the threshold stress is not very clear at present. Rosler and Arzt [31] have suggested that thermally activated detachment of a dislocation from an attractive particle in DS alloys would give the appearance of a reduced threshold stress which decreasing temperature. Mishra and Nandy [32] developed a model based on the dissociation of lattice dislocations into interfacial dislocations, when lattice dislocations enter the matrix-interface during the creep of DS alloys. They have argued that the strong temperature dependence of τ_0 observed in DS alloys may arise from the sensitivity of the dissociation reaction to temperature. More recently, Mohamed *et al.* [4, 18] have speculated that the strong temperature dependence of the threshold stress may be relate to the segregation of impurities to dislocations that are captured at the detachment side of dispersion particles. This speculation is consistent with some observations documented in references [7, 18, 32-34], and is further supported by the present investigation: the Zn-22%Al/7vol.%SiC composite showed higher threshold stress than its reinforcement-free counterpart while the values of activation energy, Q_o , are exactly same for both materials. The presence of reinforcement particles influenced the apparent creep characteristics in region I (higher n and Q_a) by causing an increased threshold stress. However, the reinforcement particles made no observable contribution to the activation energy for threshold stress, indicating that the origins of the temperature dependence are basically the same for both composite and the alloy. Impurity atom segregation may occur at dislocations located along grain boundaries in the alloy

while at the dislocations captured at the detachment side of the incoherent particles in the composite. If binding between impurity atoms and dislocations is strong and if the mobility of impurity atoms is very low, a threshold stress must be exceeded before dislocations can break away from the impurity atmosphere and continue moving. The breaking-away processes (or segregation drag on moving dislocations) are same in nature for the two materials, leading to identical activation energy and temperature dependence for threshold stress.

Correlation between the deformation mechanisms for region I and II

The interpretation of the creep behavior of Zn-22%Al/7vol.%SiC composite in terms of τ_0 arising from particulate/dislocation interactions signifies that regions II and I are controlled by the same deformation mechanism. Previous work [8] on Zn-22%Al alloy showed that, with the absence of τ_0 , the creep behavior for region II and I would be identical, i.e., region II would dominate the whole range of strain rates, and that the τ_0 arising from boundary segregation is the origin of region I. In the present investigation on the composite material, with the presence of a τ_0 with higher magnitude (by ~ 4 times) and different source (particulate/dislocation interaction), the identity of the deformation mechanisms for region I and region II is further supported by two observations: (1) although the increased τ_0 in the composite changed the apparent creep behavior in region I (higher n and Q), this τ_0 is only associated with region I and it does not destroy the fundamental process of creep flow in region II (n and Q remain unchanged); (2) the extension of region I, i.e., the shift of the transition region between region I and region II towards higher stress level, suggested that the narrowing of region II with increasing τ_0 is a gradual process and there are no fundamental (or sharp) changes that are responsible for distinguishing region I from region II.

CONCLUSIONS

The creep behaviors of Zn-22%Al/7%SiC(p) composite were investigated and the microstructures of the starting and deformed materials were characterized using SEM and TEM. The mechanical data were analyzed with reference to that of its reinforcement-free counterparts. The threshold stress for the creep of Zn-22%Al/7%SiC(p) composite, τ_0 , was measured to be about four times higher than that in reinforcement-free Zn-22%Al alloy. This increased τ_0 was attributed to the interaction between dislocations and ultra-fine dispersion particles. The strong temperature dependence of τ_0 was suggested as a reflection of an interaction between impurities that are able to segregate at incoherent particles and dislocations that are captured at the detachment side of the particles. The analysis of the experimental data based on the concept of threshold stress, τ_0 , signified that region I and II are controlled by the same deformation mechanism.

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